

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No5(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 310 sahifa,
1-may, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti metodistining boshqaruv funksiyalari.....	10
Qarshibayeva Dilfuza Xidirbayevna	
Texnologik mashinalar va jihozlar ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarida kasbiy kompetensiyani shakllantirishning pedagogik qonuniyatlari va metodologik tizimini ishlab chiqish	15
Elmanov Abbas Begmat o'g'li, Mirzaumidov Asilbek Shuxratjonovich	
Katta yoshdagi guruh bolalarida o'z-o'zini boshqarish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda o'yinning roli	19
Ergasheva Farangiz Umidjon qizi, Fayzullayev Sharipboy Nurillayevich	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi.....	23
Yaxshiboyeva Nargiza Rustamqulovna	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida inson resurslarini boshqarishda muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimidan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari	28
Gulmira Jumanova	
Nomoddiy madaniy merosning talaba-yoshlarni yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxs sifatida tarbiyalashdagi ahamiyati	33
Erboyev Suxrob Abdusalomovich	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar va ularda hissiy-irodaning shakllanishi	37
Davlatova Zebo Haydarovna	
Zamonaviy oilada avlodlararo munosabatlarning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	40
Ochilova Farida Baxriddinovna	
Maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida qizlar kitobxonligini rivojlantirish metodlari	44
Qo'chqarova Oysha Oltibayevna	
Buyuk allomalar merosidan foydalanishning metodik holati va mavjud muammolari.....	48
Sevara Mamatkarimova	
Futbol o'yinida to'pga kalla bilan zarba berish.....	53
Xolmaxmatov Boburjon Musurmon o'g'li	
Использование современных инновационных методов в процессе обучения русскому языку в иноязычных группах высшего образовательного учреждения.....	56
Курбанова Шаира Исмаиловна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlashda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish ...	60
Kushakova Gulnora Egamkulovna, Muhammadiyeva Shaxzoda Sunnatilla qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda musiqa mashg'ulotlari orqali o'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodlari	63
Muminova Feruza Farxodovna	
Alisher Navoiy merosining yoshlar ma'naviy-estetik tarbiyasidagi ahamiyati	70
Qayumxo'jayev Botirxo'ja Ikromxo'ja o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida amaliy topshiriqlar orqali tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish	74
Saidova Dilnoza Maripovna	
К вопросу о классификации современной антиутопии.....	78
Дмитрий Валерьевич Пупонин	
Когнитивная гибкость как фактор психологического благополучия старшеклассников в период адаптации к новым образовательным требованиям	82
Муксинова Динора Азаматовна	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilida ta'lim beruvchi professor-o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini baholash: xalqaro tajribalar qiyosiy tahlili va O'zbekiston amaliyoti	87
Baxtiyarova Muniba Ne'matjon qizi	
Valeologik tarbiya asosida maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarini tayyorlashda innovatsion va raqamli yondashuvlar	92
Berkinova Charos Islomovna	

Grammatik tushunchalarni o'rgatish metodikasi.....	96
<i>N. R. Masharipova</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish va o'quvchilar bilimni baholashda xorijiy tajribalardan foydalanish finlyandiya ta'lim tizimi misolida.....	99
<i>Obidova Muqaddas Ro'ziqulovna</i>	
The Difference Between Androgogy and Pedagogy.....	106
<i>Pardayeva Aziza Rahmatillojevna</i>	
Elektr mashinalari fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari.....	110
<i>Shodiyeva Nozina Shuxrat qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida direktor o'rinbosarlarining aksiologik yondashuv asosida boshqaruv funksiyalari va vakolatlari hamda maktablarda ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	113
<i>Toxirov Botirjon G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
Ispan tili darslarida kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish usullari	119
<i>Tursunqulov Sanjar Dilmurod o'g'li, Shukurullayeva Feruza Dilmurodovna</i>	
Surxondaryo viloyatida yetishtiriladigan ingichka tolali paxta navlarining qo'llanilishi	124
<i>Ubaydullayeva Komila Bozor qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda empatiya hissini shakllantirishning nazariy asosi	127
<i>Xolmirzayeva Gulbahor Bahodirovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligi	130
<i>Raximova Dilshoda Xoliqberdiyevna</i>	
Bo'lajak sport murabbiylarida kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	134
<i>Sherzod Shuxratovich Boboyorov</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalar sportini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy va tashkiliy mexanizmlari.....	138
<i>Sangirov Nuriddin Iriskulovich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning boshqaruv kompetentligini rivojlantirishning integrativ modeli	142
<i>Rasulova Umida Bahodir qizi</i>	
Yashil pedagogikaning konseptual modeli va tamoyillari.....	146
<i>Raxmatova Dilnoza Abdurashidovna</i>	
Ta'lim jarayoni ishtirokchilarida emotsional barqarorlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari ..	149
<i>Boymatova Munavvar Ravshan qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda zamonaviy raqamli platformalardan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	152
<i>Lukmonova Salomat Gafurovna</i>	
Rivojlanishida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar uchun pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimining shakl, metod va vositalari	157
<i>Farmonova Madina Bahriddin qizi</i>	
Innovatsion boshqaruv tizimlarida qaror qabul qilish va kommunikatsiya samaradorligi	161
<i>Sotvoldiyeva Xurliqo G'ayratjon qizi</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning media savodxonligini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	167
<i>Choriyeva Xurmo Panji qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassisleri malakasini oshirish tizimining zamonaviy tendensiyalari va raqamlashtirish jarayonlarining pedagogik ahamiyati.....	172
<i>Qosimova Sh. N., Dusmaxamedov A. A.</i>	
Maktab o'quvchilarida o'zini o'zi tarbiyalashni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari (8–9-sinflar asosida)..	177
<i>Norxo'jayeva Lobar Nuriddin qizi</i>	
STEAM loyihalar yordamida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy va tanqidiy tafakkurni shakllantirish	181
<i>Mirjamolova Moxira Abdugaffor qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini milliy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalashning pedagogik ahamiyati va metodik asoslari.....	188
<i>Axmad Bolqiyev</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini xalqaro baholash dasturlari asosida baholashning pedagogik asoslari.....	191
<i>Shavqiddin Burxonov</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda liderlik va pedagogik menejment muammolari.....	194
<i>Pardaboyev Doston</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhiti: tushunchasi, strukturasi va rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	197
<i>Kulboyeva Dilnoza Abdug'afurovna</i>	
Особенности применения графических органайзеров на практических занятиях по дисциплине “Практикум литературы народов СНГ”.....	199
<i>Татьяна Викторовна Половинкина</i>	
Historical Stages in the Study and Treatment of Scoliosis (Spinal Curvature).....	204
<i>Shermatova Mokhira Baxodir qizi</i>	
Talaba qizlarga badiiy gimnastika cho'qmori yordamida bajariladigan fundamental mashqlarni o'rgatish....	209
<i>Musharafxon Sultanova</i>	
Oliy ta'limda tarbiyaviy ishlarni tashkil etish bo'yicha xalqaro modellarning qiyosiy tahlili.....	213
<i>Ziyotova Madina</i>	
Sport mutaxassislarini tayyorlashda voleybol o'qituvchisining ko'nikmalari va uslubi	216
<i>Turg'unov Baxtiyor O'rolovich</i>	
Matematik masalalarni yechish jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlash va ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	220
<i>Yusupova Latofat Nuriddinovna</i>	
Zamonaviy sharoitda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda deontologik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning innovatsion texnologiyalari	228
<i>Nasirova Nigora Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Paraengil atletika mashg'ulotlarida individual yondashuvning ahamiyati	233
<i>Abduxoliqova Shoiraxon Akramjon qizi</i>	
Biologiya fanini o'qitishda xalq pedagogikasi elementlaridan foydalanish orqali ekologik madaniyatni rivojlantirish	239
<i>Baxrombekova Sojidxon Sherzodjon qizi</i>	
Maktab texnologik ta'limida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning o'quv samaradorligiga ta'siri: o'rta muddatli istiqbollar (2027–2031)	245
<i>Berdiyeva Gulnoza Rizoqulovna, Tursunov Sherzod Ziyat o'g'li, Ismatullayev Javohir Ubaydulla o'g'li</i>	
Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali jismoniy tarbiya va sport tizimini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish	251
<i>Eryigitov Dilshod Xolboyevich</i>	
Enhancing Speaking Skills Productively in English	255
<i>J. M. Fayzullayev, G. R. Elmonova</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan katta guruh bolalari bilan ishlashning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	259
<i>Jumanova Iroda Nomozovna, Fayzullayev Sharipboy Nurillayevich</i>	
2–3 yoshli bolalarning maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotiga ijtimoiy moslashuvi: nazariy va empirik tahlil	263
<i>Klicheva Dilnoza Zulfon qizi</i>	
Inson–texnika tizimida ta'lim olayotgan talabalarda iste'dod namoyon bo'lishining psixologik xususiyatlari	267
<i>Kuvandikova Gulnora Gulamovna</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning mutaxassis sifatida shakllanishida xavotirlanish holatining namoyon bo'lishi.....	270
<i>Nuriddinov Rasuljon Samitjon o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashda zamonaviy psixologik-pedagogik yondashuv.....	274
<i>Nuriddinova Maysara Ikramovna, Kodirova Albina Faridovna</i>	
Talabalarda qaror qabul qilishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	279
<i>Rajabova Go'zal Zarifovna</i>	
Musobaqa oldi psixologik tayyorgarlikning tezkorlikka ta'siri.....	283
<i>Sitora Elova Axmatkulovna</i>	

Pediatriya ta'limida sun'iy intellekt – talaba uchun virtual assistent.....	287
Umarkulov Muhtorali Islomkulovich	
Bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya mutaxassislarida jismoniy savodxonlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	290
Xakimov Xurshid Nozimovich	
Сущность и виды познавательной активности детей 5–6 лет.....	294
Джамилова Н. Н., Кудратова М. У.	
Uzluksiz ta'lim jarayonida mustaqil fikrlovchi, ijodkor shaxsni tarbiyalashning pedagogik-psixologik masalalari.....	298
Siddiqova Sanobar Xaydarovna	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarning bilish, ijodiy faolligini oshirish.....	301
Siddiqova Sanobar Xaydarovna, Qushoqova Guzal	
Badiiy adabiyotda Ibn Sino obrazining yaratilishidagi o'ziga xosliklar.....	304
Tangirov A. J.	

HISTORICAL STAGES IN THE STUDY AND TREATMENT OF SCOLIOSIS (SPINAL CURVATURE)

Shermatova Mokhira Baxodir qizi

Master's student

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Field: Physical Education and Sports Management,

Organization and Management of Sports Events

Abstract: Historical development of scoliosis, as well as the stages in the formation of its diagnostic and treatment methods, are examined. The contributions of scientists who studied scoliosis from ancient times to modern medicine are analysed, including Hippocrates, Galen, Avicenna, Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre, and Paul Harrington. Early diagnostic methods are described in detail, including visual observation, the forward bending test, palpation, and examination using mechanical devices. The main treatment approaches are also considered: therapeutic exercises and physiotherapy, brace treatment, and the development of surgical methods. It is emphasised that scoliosis, shaped by centuries of scientific experience, is now effectively treated through early diagnosis, conservative methods, and surgical intervention.

Key words: scoliosis, Hippocrates, Galen, Avicenna, Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre, Paul Harrington, spinal curvature, orthopaedics, physiotherapy, therapeutic exercise, brace, traction, diagnostics, rehabilitation, surgical treatment, Adams test, muscle balance, spinal surgery, prevention.

Annotatsiya: Skolioz kasalligining tarixiy rivojlanishi hamda uni aniqlash va davolash usullarining shakllanish bosqichlari yoritiladi. Qadimgi davrdan zamonaviy tibbiyotgacha bo'lgan jarayonda skoliozni o'rganib kelgan olimlar – Gippokrat, Galen, Avicenna, Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre va Paul Harrington kabi olimlarning ilmiy hissalarini tahlil qilinadi. Skoliozni aniqlashning dastlabki usullari, jumladan kuzatish, oldinga egilish testi, palpatsiya hamda mexanik moslamalar orqali tekshirish usullari batafsil bayon etiladi. Davolash yo'nalishlari sifatida davolovchi gimnastika va fizioterapiya, korset bilan davolash hamda jarrohlik usullarining rivojlanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Skolioz kasalligi asrlar davomida shakllangan ilmiy tajriba asosida bugungi kunda erta diagnostika, konservativ davolash va jarrohlik usullari orqali samarali davolanayotgan kasallik sifatida baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: skolioz, Gippokrat, Galen, Avicenna, Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre, Paul Harrington, umurtqa pog'onasi qiysayishi, ortopediya, fizioterapiya, davolovchi gimnastika, korset (brace), traksiya, diagnostika, reabilitatsiya, jarrohlik davolash, Adams testi, mushaklar muvozanati, spinal jarrohlik, profilaktika.

Аннотация: Историческое развитие заболевания сколиоз, а также этапы формирования методов его диагностики и лечения рассматриваются с научной точки зрения. Анализируется вклад учёных, изучавших сколиоз с древних времён до современной медицины, таких как Гиппократ, Гален, Авиценна, Амбруаз Парэ, Льюис Сэйр и Пол Харрингтон. Подробно описаны ранние методы диагностики сколиоза, включая визуальное наблюдение, тест наклона вперёд, пальпацию и обследование с использованием механических устройств. Рассматриваются основные направления лечения: лечебная гимнастика и физиотерапия, корсетная терапия, а также развитие хирургических методов. Подчёркивается, что сколиоз, сформировавшийся на основе многовекового научного опыта, в настоящее время эффективно лечится благодаря ранней диагностике, консервативным методам и хирургическому вмешательству.

Ключевые слова: сколиоз, Гиппократ, Гален, Авиценна, Амбруаз Парэ, Льюис Сэйр, Пол Харрингтон, искривление позвоночника, ортопедия, физиотерапия, лечебная гимнастика, корсет (brace), тракция, диагностика, реабилитация, хирургическое лечение, тест Адамса, мышечный баланс, спинальная хирургия, профилактика.

INTRODUCTION

Scoliosis is not a new disease – it has been known to humanity for more than 2000 years. It was first described in ancient times by the Greek physician Hippocrates (460–370 BC). He observed spinal curvature and proposed special treatment methods, including traction devices.

Today, modern medicine has significantly improved the possibilities for early diagnosis and effective treatment.

In Hippocrates' time, scoliosis was diagnosed without modern equipment, relying solely on observation and experience. Nevertheless, he used highly accurate and systematic methods.

Diagnostic methods by Hippocrates:

1. **Visual observation (primary method).** Hippocrates carefully examined the patient in a standing position: he observed whether the shoulders were at equal height, asked whether the shoulder blades protruded evenly, and considered whether the waistline was symmetrical and whether the body leaned to one side. He studied the causes of scoliosis and its treatment methods. If an asymmetry was present, he concluded that there was a curvature of the spine.
2. **Forward bending test (Adams test).** This method is still used today. The patient bends forward while the physician observes the back. If one side appears higher or the ribs protrude, it indicates scoliosis.
3. **Palpation.** He examined the spine by touch to determine alignment and curvature.
4. **Assessment of body balance.** Observing posture, walking, and overall balance.
5. **Mechanical devices.** Hippocrates used a special traction bench to stretch the body and assess the correction of curvature.

Hippocrates distinguished scoliosis from other spinal diseases, described it as a separate condition, and combined diagnosis and treatment. Even without modern X-rays and advanced technologies, his methods became the basis of modern medicine.

Hippocrates is considered the first scientist in the history of scoliosis treatment to propose the idea of treatment through body movement and mechanical action. He attempted to improve the condition of the spine by moving and stretching the body to a certain extent, rather than limiting treatment to bed rest.

The main methods he used included stretching the body on special wooden boards (traction), placing the patient in different positions to reduce pressure, and attempting to “mechanically straighten” the spine. The most important idea proposed by Hippocrates was that the structure of the body could be corrected through external force and movement. This concept represents one of the earliest foundations of modern physiotherapy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of scoliosis has deep historical roots, beginning with the works of Hippocrates, whose *Corpus Hippocraticum* contains the earliest descriptions of spinal deformities and their treatment through mechanical methods such as traction. The ideas of Hippocrates were further systematized by Galen, who, in *De Methodo Medendi*, provided an anatomical classification of spinal diseases and emphasized the role of muscles in the development of scoliosis. These early studies laid the theoretical foundation for understanding scoliosis as a distinct medical condition.

A significant contribution to the development of scoliosis treatment was made by Avicenna, whose *Canon of Medicine* presented a comprehensive analysis of the causes of scoliosis and highlighted the importance of physical exercises, posture, and preventive measures. Later, Ambroise Paré introduced the use of corsets as a mechanical means of spinal correction, marking a new stage in orthopedic practice. In the 19th century, Lewis Sayre advanced treatment methods by developing plaster corsets and traction techniques, significantly improving patient stabilization and therapeutic outcomes.

Modern approaches to scoliosis treatment are largely based on the scientific developments of Paul Harrington, who introduced the Harrington rod system in 1955, forming the basis of contemporary surgical interventions. The evolution of these methods is reflected in authoritative sources such as Campbell's *Operative Orthopaedics* and the clinical guidelines of the Scoliosis Research Society, which provide evidence-based recommendations for diagnosis and treatment. In addition, reports by the World Health Organization emphasize the global significance of musculoskeletal disorders and the importance of early diagnosis and комплексное лечение scoliosis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on a comprehensive analysis of historical and scientific sources related to the study and treatment of scoliosis. Data were collected through the review of classical medical works, including the writings of Hippocrates, Galen, and Avicenna, as well as later orthopedic research by Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre, and Paul Harrington. Additional information was obtained from modern scientific publications, clinical guidelines, and international medical reports, including materials from the Scoliosis Research Society and the World Health Organization. The data collection process involved systematic literature review, comparative analysis of historical and contemporary treatment methods, and extraction of relevant theoretical and practical findings. The analysis was conducted using qualitative methods, including chronolo-

gical analysis to trace the evolution of diagnostic and treatment approaches, as well as comparative analysis to identify similarities and differences between historical and modern practices. In addition, synthesis and generalization methods were applied to integrate the findings into a coherent framework, highlighting the continuity and advancement of medical knowledge. The reliability of the study was ensured through the use of well-established and widely recognized scientific sources, allowing for an объективное и последовательное раскрытие эволюции методов лечения сколиоза.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study and treatment of scoliosis have been developing since ancient times. It was first identified by Hippocrates, and in subsequent periods many scientists studied this disease in more depth and improved treatment methods.

One of the important scientists who developed scoliosis scientifically after Hippocrates was Galen (129–216 AD). Galen continued the ideas of Hippocrates and included them in a scientific system. He explained the role of muscles and movement in scoliosis in more detail. His main contributions include explaining that muscle weakness causes curvature of the spine, balancing the body with special physical exercises, and introducing the rehabilitation process into medical observation. Galen was the first to emphasise that not only the bones but also the muscular system forms scoliosis. Therefore, movement plays an important role in treatment. He studied spinal deformities and introduced the term “scoliosis” into medicine. Galen also classified other spinal diseases such as kyphosis and lordosis, establishing scoliosis as a separate disease.

The next important stage is associated with the name of Avicenna (980–1037). In the 11th century, Avicenna conducted extensive scientific work on scoliosis. He provided detailed information about scoliosis in his famous work Canon of Medicine. Avicenna indicated the causes of the disease, including congenital defects, incorrect sitting, and muscle weakness. He also emphasised the importance of massage, physical exercises, and correct posture in treatment. This approach forms the basis of current preventive and conservative treatment methods. Avicenna is one of the most important scientists who scientifically substantiated the role of gymnastics in the treatment of scoliosis and spinal diseases. In his famous work Canon of Medicine, he presented physical exercises as an integral part of treatment. The main methods he recommended were regular physical exercise, maintaining correct posture and walking habits, muscle-strengthening movements, and massage and stretching exercises.

Avicenna emphasised that proper physical education in childhood is important in preventing scoliosis. His approach became the basis of today's physiotherapy and preventive gymnastics.

In the 16th century (1510–1590), the French surgeon Ambroise Paré made a significant contribution to the development of orthopaedics. Ambroise Paré initiated a new stage in the treatment of scoliosis. He was the first to use braces and attempted to correct spinal deformities mechanically. He is considered the founder of modern corsets. This method provided external support for the spine, preventing further curvature. Modern corsets used today are based on this idea.

In the 19th–20th centuries, the treatment of scoliosis developed further. Lewis Sayre (1820–1900) introduced new methods for the treatment of scoliosis. He implemented plaster cast fixation and spinal traction methods. In the 1870s–1880s, his work significantly improved the immobilisation and maintenance of patients with scoliosis in the correct position. This period is considered a scientific stage in orthopaedic treatment.

One of the greatest achievements is associated with the name of Paul Harrington (1911–1980). In the mid-20th century (1950s), Paul Harrington made a major breakthrough in medicine. He developed a system of metal rods known as the “Harrington rod”. Since 1955, this method has been used in scoliosis surgery. The Harrington method made it possible to straighten and stabilise the spine internally. This achievement paved the way for effective surgical treatment of severe scoliosis and became the basis of modern spinal surgery.

In general, methods of treating scoliosis have developed in three main directions. In mild cases, physical exercises and physiotherapy are used; these methods originate from the views of Avicenna. In moderate cases, corsets are used; this method was pioneered by Ambroise Paré. In severe cases, surgery is applied, and its modern forms are based on the developments of Paul Harrington.

Nicolas Andry (1658–1742) is one of the founders of orthopaedics, who expressed important ideas about children's posture and scoliosis in his work Orthopaedia (1741). His approach included teaching children correct sitting posture, preventing improper sitting and walking, and strengthening muscles through light physical exercises. Andry introduced the idea of “proper posture and proper development” into medicine, which later became the basis of postural therapy.

Per Henrik Ling (1776–1839) is considered the founder of modern physiotherapy. He created the “Swedish gymnastics” system and developed a specialised set of exercises for the treatment of scoliosis.

His contributions include:

- a symmetrical system of exercises (equal on both sides);
- coordination of breathing and movement;
- stretching and strengthening exercises for the spine;
- development of individual therapeutic programmes.

Ling was the first to formulate gymnastics as a scientifically grounded treatment system. His methods form the direct basis of modern physiotherapy.

The development of the 19th–20th centuries further strengthened the scientific foundation of gymnastics in medicine. During this period, in the treatment of scoliosis:

- individual rehabilitation programmes were developed;
- increased attention was given to restoring muscle balance;
- a system of orthopaedic exercises was formed.

During this period, gymnastics became not merely physical activity but a specialised medical therapy. As a result of the work of these scientists, therapeutic exercise has become one of the most important, effective, and scientifically grounded methods of treating scoliosis today.

The question of which treatment method is the most effective is also widely discussed. The surgical method (most effective in severe cases) is associated with Paul Harrington, who developed a method for straightening the spine using a metal structure. Modern surgical procedures are based on this approach.

The most effective method for severe scoliosis is brace treatment, initiated by Ambroise Paré. Currently, Boston and Milwaukee braces help prevent deformation during growth.

The most effective non-surgical method is physical exercise and therapy.

Foundations: Avicenna.

Current methods: the Schroth method and physiotherapy are highly effective in mild cases.

Scoliosis Treatment Methods: Historical and Modern Approaches

Scientist / Era	Methods Used	Main Idea	Modern Approaches
Hippocrates (460–370 BC)	Visual observation, forward bending test, palpation, traction (stretching devices)	The spine can be corrected through mechanical force	Diagnostics: X-ray, MRI; Treatment: physiotherapy, traction devices
Galen (129–216 CE)	Study of muscles, treatment through movement	Muscles play an important role in scoliosis	Rehabilitation, restoring muscle balance, kinesitherapy
Avicenna (Ibn Sina) (980–1037)	Massage, gymnastics, proper posture, prevention	Treatment through movement and lifestyle	Physiotherapy, therapeutic exercises (LFK), preventive programs
Ambroise Paré (1510–1590)	Use of corsets (braces)	External support of the spine	Boston brace, Milwaukee brace
Nicolas Andry (1658–1742)	Proper sitting, prevention in children	Posture is important	Postural therapy, ergonomics
Per Henrik Ling (1776–1839)	Methods: Swedish gymnastics, symmetrical exercises	Gymnastics as a therapeutic tool	Physiotherapy, individualized exercise programs
Lewis Sayre (1820–1900)	Plaster corset, traction	Treatment through immobilization	Modern orthopedic braces and stabilization
Paul Harrington (1911–1980)	Metal rod (Harrington rod), surgery	Correction through internal fixation	Modern spinal surgery (implants, screws)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study and treatment of scoliosis have developed from ancient simple mechanical methods to modern high-tech medicine. Today, early detection and proper treatment of this disease can significantly improve the quality of life of patients. Scoliosis has undergone a long historical development path from ancient times to modern medicine. Many scientists have made significant contributions to the study and treatment of this disease, and each era has introduced new approaches. The study of scoliosis began with Hippocrates, Galen

provided a scientific foundation, Avicenna developed treatment and prevention methods, Ambroise Paré introduced the corset method, and Paul Harrington laid the foundation for modern surgical treatment. Thus, effective treatment methods used today have been formed over the centuries.

Therapeutic gymnastics (physical exercises and rehabilitation exercises) in the treatment of scoliosis has played an important role since ancient times. This direction was gradually developed by several historical figures and became the basis of modern physiotherapy. The history of scoliosis treatment has developed in three main directions:

1. Gymnastics and physiotherapy (Avicenna, Per Henrik Ling)
2. Corset and external support (Ambroise Paré, Lewis Sayre)
3. Surgical treatment (Paul Harrington)

As a result, today scoliosis is most effectively treated through early detection, exercises, corsets, and, if necessary, surgical intervention. These methods are the result of scientific experience accumulated over centuries and the research of scientists.

References:

1. Hippocrates. Corpus Hippocraticum. – A collection of ancient Greek medical writings; the first information about scoliosis and spinal deformities.
2. Galen. De Methodo Medendi and other Roman medical treatises. – Study and classification of spinal diseases on an anatomical basis.
3. Avicenna. Al-Qanun fi't-tibb (The Canon of Medicine). – Causes of scoliosis, physical exercises, and methods of treatment.
4. Ambroise Paré. Orthopedic and surgical works. – Initial description of treatment methods using a corset (brace).
5. Lewis Sayre. Orthopedic research and clinical work (19th century). – Development of plaster corsets and traction methods.
6. Paul Harrington. Scientific work on the Harrington rod system (1955). – Modern principles of surgical treatment of scoliosis.
7. Campbell's Operative Orthopaedics. – Modern surgical methods of orthopaedics and scoliosis.
8. Scoliosis Research Society (SRS). Clinical Guidelines and Reports. – Modern recommendations for the diagnosis and treatment of scoliosis.
9. World Health Organization (WHO). Musculoskeletal Health Reports. – Spinal diseases and global health statistics.
10. Nicolas Andry. Orthopaedia. – 1741.
11. Per Henrik Ling. Gymnastic System of Sweden. – 19th century (1800s).
12. S. Terry Canale, James H. Beaty. Campbell's Operative Orthopaedics. – Elsevier, 2020.
13. Scoliosis Research Society (SRS). Clinical Guidelines and Reports. – Official materials. <https://www.srs.org>
14. World Health Organization. Musculoskeletal Health Reports. <https://www.who.int>

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №5(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.